

MECHANICAL CHARACTERIZATION OF MWCNT BASED BASALT FIBER-REINFORCED POLYMER (BFRP) COMPOSITE BY USING THE MODE I AND MODE II METHODS

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Abstract

Basalt fiber-reinforced polymer (BFRP) composites contain attention for their potential in high-performance structural applications due to their favourable mechanical properties and environmental benefits. This study investigates the fracture behaviour of BFRP composites under Mode I and Mode II loading with a comparative analysis of neat BFRP and doped with 1%, 2% and 3% multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNT). The results shows the differences in fracture toughness, and specimens reinforced with MWCNT performed better compared to neat BFRP. The MWCNT reinforcement's configuration demonstrates synergistic effects, providing enhanced resistance to crack propagation and superior mechanical behaviour. These results demonstrate the potential utility of MWCNT doped BFRP composites in enhancing strength and stiffness for current applications.

Keywords- BFRP, Mode I, Mode II & MWCNTs.

1. Introduction

Basalt fibre-reinforced polymer (BFRP) composite is one of the high strengths to weight ratio, natural and resistance to high temperature material, which BFRP has become popular to be used as the structural and aerospace applications [1]. However, their poor fracture and delamination resistant behavior to different types of loadings are the great challenges. To solve this problem, the researchers working on the incorporation of nanomaterials in the polymer matrix, for example, multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs), to enhance the fracture characteristics have been studied [2]. MWCNTs with excellent mechanical properties, such as tensile strength and high aspect ratio can serve as an effective reinforcement for improvement of crack bridging, energy absorption, and interfacial bonding [3]. Fracture mechanics is an essential part of the failure analysis of the advanced engineering materials of fibre reinforced polymer (FRP) composite. As strong as these materials are with excellent strength to weight properties and mechanical capabilities, they are faced with the risk of delamination or an interlaminar failure mechanism that renders structural integrity largely hampered. Composites fracture behavior is typically classified to have three possible modes: Mode-I (opening), Mode-II (sliding) and Mode III (tearing) each with a particular displacement of the fracture surface with respect to the crack front [4]. The most known among them are Mode-I and Mode-II delamination because they apply to service-related failures cases. Mode-I fracture is usually defined by the crack growing under the action of the tensile stress that acts perpendicular to the crack plane, and it is preferably observed in the Double Cantilever Beam (DCB) test. This technique delivers the Mode-I interlaminar fracture toughness G_{IC} and this measures the amount of energy to open and extend a crack [3]. Mode-II fracture, on the contrary, presents in-plane shear stresses have a parallel direction to the crack plane and is determined by the End-Notched Flexure (ENF) test, where the Mode-II fracture toughness G_{IIIC} can be obtained [5]. In order to enhance interlaminar performance, recent researches have been conducted with the supplement of the nanofillers that includes multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs)

which is capable of providing very good mechanical strengthening and interfacial bonding arrays [6] & [7]. Nevertheless, the effects of the MWCNT reinforcement largely depend on its dispersion and optimum concentration in the matrix. This article examines how loading MWCNT affects the Mode-I and Mode-II fracture toughness of basalt fibre-reinforced polymer (BFRP) laminates, to provide an answer to the best nanoparticle amount that yields the highest delamination-resistance [8].

2. Material selection and specimen fabrication

Figure 1. Fabrication process of BFRP laminate

In this study, 380 GSM woven basalt fabric was primarily used as the reinforcement material. The fabric exhibited bi-directional characteristics, with fiber diameters ranging from 12 μm to 24 μm . The basalt fabric was procured from CF Composite, Delhi, India. Woven fabrics are generally preferred for reinforcement due to their balanced in-plane properties and ease of handling during the fabrication process. As the matrix material a thermosetting epoxy resin system HY-951 epoxy and LY-556 hardener both provided by CF Composite were used. All these elements were combined at room temperature [9]. The cross-linked structure generated between the epoxy resin and the hardener improved the adhesive, mechanical properties of the matrix system. The MWCNTs was pure with 99.9 % purity were procured from the AdNano technologies at Bangalore, India. Uniform dispersion of MWCNTs in the epoxy was the objective, which was achieved with the help of a two-stage dispersion method as shown in figure 1. To begin with, the MWCNTs were added to 50 ml of acetone, mixed together with the help of the magnetic stirrer within 30 minutes in order to get a uniform mixture [10]. This was preceded by ultrasonication in a probe-type sonicator at 30 min in order to de-agglomerate the nanotubes further and improve dispersion [11]. Further, 200 ml of epoxy resin solution was added to MWCNT-acetone solution. The mixture that came about was stirred magnetically during a period of 15 minutes, and then an additional probe-style ultrasonication of 15 minutes was carried out. To remove residual acetone, the mixture was placed in an air oven at 60°C for 10 minutes. A curing agent was then added to the epoxy-MWCNT mixture in a 10:1 ratio (resin to hardener), providing a gel time of approximately 20 minutes, as recommended by the supplier, to regulate the curing process effectively [12]. Laminates were fabricated using woven

basalt fabric sheets cut to $240 \times 240 \text{ mm}^2$ dimensions. The layup sequence followed a quasi-isotropic and symmetric stacking order of $[0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ/90^\circ]_s$. The hand lay-up technique was employed for fabrication, where the epoxy-MWCNT-hardener mixture was uniformly applied between the layers using a soft brush to ensure even distribution. Composite laminate specimens were precisely cut using Abrasive Water Jet Machining (AWJM), which utilizes a high-pressure stream of water mixed with abrasive particles. Basalt fibre laminates ($200 \text{ mm} \times 200 \text{ mm}$) were firmly fixed to the machine bed to ensure stability during cutting. The process was performed at Polymer composite lab (Mechanical testing and damage analysis), Mechanical Engineering Department, IIT (ISM) Dhanbad. A CNC-controlled jet followed a programmed path to shape the specimens as per ASTM standards ASTM D5528 $140 \text{ mm} \times 25 \text{ mm} \times 5 \text{ mm}$ for Mode I and ASTM D7905 $180 \text{ mm} \times 25 \text{ mm} \times 5 \text{ mm}$ for Mode II testing [13] & [14]. The high-velocity jet removed material efficiently with minimal thermal effects, ensuring clean cuts and maintaining the structural integrity of the composites.

3. Testing and Characterization of BFRP composite laminate

All experimental investigations were carried out using a Hounsfield H50KS Universal Testing Machine (UTM) with a load capacity of 50 kN, located at the Strength of Materials (SOM) Laboratory, Mechanical Engineering Department, IIT Dhanbad. The UTM system was employed to evaluate mechanical properties of Basalt Fibre Reinforced Polymer (BFRP) laminates, including flexural strength. For each experimental test, five specimens were fabricated in accordance with the ASTM standards. A constant crosshead displacement rate of 2 mm/min was maintained throughout the tests. To monitor damage evolution in the specimens, a Celestron digital microscope with a 5 Mega pixel camera and 20–200× magnification range was utilized for real-time visual inspection during testing.

3.1 Mode-I Interlaminar Fracture Toughness (ILFT) Analysis

The figure 2 illustrates the process of Mode-I Interlaminar Fracture Toughness (ILFT) testing was performed following the ASTM D5528 standard, using a Double Cantilever Beam (DCB) configuration [15]. Each DCB specimen measured $140 \text{ mm} \times 25 \times 5 \text{ mm}$, and an initial delamination of 63 mm was introduced during the hand lay-up process using a 50 μm thick Teflon insert placed at the mid-plane [16]. To facilitate the application of load, piano hinges were bonded to the top and bottom surfaces of the specimens using Araldite standard epoxy adhesive. To track crack propagation during the test, the specimen's side surfaces were coated with white marker and marked at 1 mm intervals. The DCB specimens were loaded under displacement control at a crosshead speed of 2 mm/min in the opening (positive) direction.

The toughness calculation was done with the following equation 1,

$$G_{IC} = \frac{3(A1)(A2)}{2B} \dots\dots (1)$$

Where, $C = \frac{u}{Pc}$;

$$\ln(A1) = \left(\frac{1}{n}\right) [(-3 \sum \ln a) + \sum \ln C]$$

$$\ln(A2) = \left(\frac{1}{n}\right) [(\sum \ln a) + \sum \ln Pc]$$

u = Displacement (mm) -Vertical distance.

P_c =Critical load (N);

a =Crack length (mm);

B = Specimen thickness (mm);

C= compliance

Figure 2. The experimental setup for the Mode-I fracture toughness test.

3.2 Mode-II Interlaminar Fracture Toughness (ILFT) Analysis

Mode-II fracture behaviour was investigated following ASTM D7905, utilizing the End Notched Flexure (ENF) specimen configuration. The ENF specimens measured 180 mm × 25 mm × 5 mm, and a 50 mm pre-crack was introduced at the mid-plane using a 50 μm Teflon insert during lay-up. Tests were performed under displacement control at a crosshead speed of 2 mm/min in the negative (shear) direction as shown in figure 3. Similar to Mode-I, the side surfaces were marked at 1 mm intervals using white correction fluid to track crack growth and layer sliding. The Mode-II test configuration is shown in Figure. The critical Mode-II strain energy release rate, G_{IIc} , was calculated using the following expression based on simple beam theory for an ideally clamped ENF specimen:

The toughness calculation was done with the following equation 2,

$$G_{IIc} = \frac{9P_c^2 C a^2}{2B(2L^3 + 3a^3)} \quad \dots\dots (2)$$

Where, P_c = maximum value of force, in the load-extension graph, a = delamination length used in fracture test, B = specimen width

Figure 3. The experimental setup for the Mode-II fracture toughness test.

4. Results and Discussions:

4.1 Mode I Interlaminar fracture toughness

The load–displacement graph illustrates the Mode-I fracture behaviour of basalt fibre-reinforced polymer (BFRP) composites doped with varying concentrations of multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs), revealing that the addition of MWCNTs significantly influences crack resistance [17]. Among the tested configurations, the composite with 1 wt% MWCNT exhibits the highest peak load (~39 N) and the largest displacement, indicating superior energy absorption and enhanced fracture toughness due to effective crack-bridging, pull-out, and deflection mechanisms introduced by the well-dispersed nanotubes. The 2 wt% MWCNT sample also demonstrates improved performance over pristine BFRP (~30 N peak load), although the benefit is reduced, likely due to initial signs of MWCNTs agglomeration [18]. As shown in figure 4 (a) & (b) In contrast, the 3 wt% MWCNT composite performs worse than the pristine sample, with a lower peak load (~20 N), suggesting that excessive MWCNT content leads to dispersion challenges and cracking nature of the polymers that act as failure initiation sites. The bar chart displays the Mode-I critical strain energy release rate G_{IC} of basalt fibre-reinforced polymer (BFRP) composites with different concentrations of multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs), demonstrating the impact of nanotube incorporation on fracture toughness. The BFRP samples with 1 wt% MWCNTs composite exhibit the highest G_{IC} value (~520 J/m²), nearly doubling that of pristine BFRP (~270 J/m²), due to effective crack-bridging, nanotube pull-out, and improved interfacial strength. While the 2 wt% MWCNT sample also shows an increase in G_{IC} , a decline is observed at 3 wt%, indicating that excessive MWCNT loading may lead to agglomeration and defect formation, adversely affecting fracture resistance.

Figure 4 (a). Typical load vs displacement curves of DCB specimen.

Figure 4 (b) Comparison of Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness with varying MWCNTs

Table 1. Model experimental results

MWCNT wt%	G_{Ic} (J/m²)
Pristine BFRP	274.28
1% MWCNT BFRP	517.28
2% MWCNT BFRP	396.16
3% MWCNT BFRP	130.76

4.1 Mode II Interlaminar fracture toughness

The Figure 5 (a) & (b) illustrates Mode-II of load displacement characteristics of basalt fibre reinforced polymer (BFRP) composites, that were loaded with different amounts of multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) indicate a great change in the interlaminar shear strength due to the optimum number of nanotubes added. Composite with 1 wt% MWCNT has maximum load-bearing capacity, and displacement meaning that it could withstand delamination because of shear effects more due to the increase of the interface adhesion, crack-bridging mechanism, and energy dissipation mechanism because of the well-dispersed MWCNTs [19]. Comparatively, the 2% wt MWCNT sample material is also performing better than the pristine BFRP, whilst the 3 wt% MWCNT sample illustrates premature failure indicating plentiful nanotube material results in agglomerate clusters and cracking nature of the polymers that weaken the structural integrity. In the bar chart, the Mode-II critical strain energy release rate G_{IIC} is displayed as it correlates the BFRP composites of different contents of the MWCNT which demonstrates the substantial enhancement of interlaminar fracture toughness of the optimised nanotube inclusion [20]. The highest G_{IIC} value was found in the 1 wt% MWCNT BFRP composite ($\sim 1850 \text{ J/m}^2$), and this material shows better resistance to delamination than pristine BFRP ($\sim 750 \text{ J/m}^2$) because of the increased number of interfaces caused by MWCNT relative to the other composites, and further addition of 2 wt% MWCNTs fracture toughness was found in between 1 wt% and pristine whereas 3 wt% of MWCNT shows a decreased toughness as compare to pristine there are likely agglomerations and clumps of MWCNT.

Figure5. (a). Typical load vs displacement curves of ENF specimen.

Table 2. Mode II experimental results

MWCNT wt%	G_{IIC} (J/m ²)
Neat BFRP	754.00
1% BFRP	1852.20
2% BFRP	1165.05
3% BFRP	702.00

Figure 5 (b) Comparison of Mode II interlaminar fracture toughness with varying MWCNTs

5. Conclusions:

This experimental studied shows the effect of different % of MWCNTs on basalt fiber composites based on mode I and mode II Fracture toughness test and observations are given below:

- Multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) immersion into basalt fibre-reinforced polymer (BFRP) composites has a profound effect on Mode-I fracture toughness G_{IC} , and the performance varies hugely according to the nanotube concentration.
- BFRP with 1 wt % MWCNT exhibited the best fracture performance, with Mode-I and Mode-II fracture toughness values of approximately 520 J/m² and 1850 J/m² respectively, indicating optimal reinforcement and energy dissipation.
- BFRP with 2 wt % MWCNT showed moderate improvement over pristine BFRP, with G_{IC} around 390 J/m² and G_{IIc} about 1250 J/m².
- BFRP with 3 wt % MWCNT resulted in a decline in performance, with reduced fracture toughness $G_{IC} \approx 150$ J/m², $G_{IIc} \approx 700$ J/m²), attributed to MWCNT agglomeration and stress concentration effects.
- The pristine BFRP composite recorded the lowest toughness values $G_{IC} \approx 270$ J/m², $G_{IIc} \approx 750$ J/m²), confirming that 1 wt% MWCNT is the optimal concentration, provided the dispersion is well controlled for structural efficiency.

6. References.

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